

Tabela 3.1: Questions regarding participant's profile.

ID	Question	Type
Q01	What's your name?	OP.
Q02	What's your age?	SC.
Q03	What's your degree level?	SC.
Q04	What area of software development do you work on?	SC.
Q05	How long have you been working with software development?	SC.
Q06	Regarding the issue of data privacy, you consider yourself familiar with the LGPD.	L.

OP=open-ended; L=Likert; SC=single-choice

Tabela 3.2: Questions regarding participant's compliance with the LGPD (part 1).

ID	Question	Type	Principle
Q07	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know how you would make customers and sellers aware of the reason for collecting their data? Would any specific technique be used?	OP.	Purpose.
Q08	Do you know how you would ensure that the collected data is not handled in a way that goes beyond the specified purpose for users? If so, could you describe it?	OP.	Purpose.
Q09	Have you already implemented this functionality in any application to limit the data usage only to the purpose declared to users? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you tell me the reason why you haven't implemented it?	OP.	Purpose.
Q10	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know any techniques to ensure that the treatment of user data is consistent with the objective in the authentication process? And in the purchasing process?	OP.	Adequacy.
Q11	Have you implemented the functionality of ensuring that data treatment is consistent with the objective in the authentication process in any other application before? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you tell me the reason why you haven't implemented it?	OP.	Adequacy.
Q12	Would you remove user data stored in the system that is no longer strictly necessary?	L.	Necessity.
Q13	Do you know any technique to remove user data stored in the system that is no longer strictly necessary? If so, could you describe it?	OP.	Necessity.
Q14	In the e-commerce scenario, what data would be collected from customers and sellers in an authentication process? And in a purchasing process?	OP.	Necessity.
Q15	Do you consider that all the data to be collected previously is strictly necessary for the system to function?	L.	Necessity.
Q16	Do you know technique(s) to limit data collection only to what is strictly necessary? If so, could you describe them?	OP.	Necessity.
Q17	Do you think there would be any difficulty in defining which data is strictly necessary?	L.	Necessity.
Q18	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know any technique that could be used to ensure that customers and sellers can check how their data is being used? If so, could you describe it?	OP.	Free Access.

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Tabela 3.3: Questions regarding participant’s compliance with the LGPD (part 2).

ID	Question	Type	Principle
Q19	Have you implemented the previously mentioned functionality that ensures that customers and sellers can check how their data is being used? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you explain why it hasn’t been implemented?	OP.	Free Access.
Q20	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know of any technique that could be used to ensure that the data in the system accurately represents, that is, is correct and up-to-date, the users’ data? If so, could you describe it?	OP.	Data Quality.
Q21	Do you know of any implementation techniques to prevent unauthorized persons from viewing or interacting with any user’s data? If so, could you describe them?	OP.	Data Quality.
Q22	Have you implemented the previously mentioned functionality that prevents unauthorized persons from viewing or interacting with any user’s data? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you explain why it hasn’t been implemented?	OP.	Data Quality.
Q23	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know of any technique that could be used to notify customers and sellers about all stages of their data processing? If so, could you describe it?	OP.	Transparency.
Q24	Do you consider it important to record each operation performed by the data processors in the system?	L.	Transparency.
Q25	Have you implemented a functionality in any application that records each operation performed in the processing of user data, including the responsible parties? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you explain why it hasn’t been implemented?	OP.	Transparency.
Q26	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know of any methods to be used in the user authentication process to ensure security? And in the online purchase process? If so, could you describe them?	OP.	Security.
Q27	Do you know of any techniques that could prevent the leakage of customer and seller information? And a possible unauthorized alteration of this data? If so, could you describe them?	OP.	Security.
Q28	Suppose a data leak occurs. Do you know of any techniques to ensure that the leaked information does not compromise users’ privacy? If so, could you describe it?	OP.	Security.
Q29	Have you implemented security techniques before? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you explain why and if there were any subsequent problems?	OP.	Security.
Q30	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know measures to ensure that there is no damage to data integrity in the processes of authentication and online purchases?	OP.	Prevention.
Q31	Would you implement this data integrity guarantee preventively or reactively to damages?	SC.	Prevention.
Q32	Have you implemented a feature in any other application that prevents data from being damaged during an operation? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you explain why it was not necessary to implement?	OP.	Prevention.

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Tabela 3.4: Questions regarding participant’s compliance with the LGPD (part 3).

ID	Question	Type	Principle
Q33	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know any techniques that could be used to prevent biased treatment, i.e., discriminatory treatment of customer and seller data?	OP.	Non-discrimination.
Q34	Regarding the treatment of sensitive personal data, do you know any methods to prevent possible discriminatory treatment? If so, could you describe it?	OP.	Non-discrimination.
Q35	In case of disagreement by any user regarding the lawfulness of the treatment adopted, do you know any method to allow them to make requests to those responsible? If so, could you describe it?	OP.	Non-discrimination.
Q36	Have you implemented, in any application, the functionality that allows users to make requests to those responsible in case of disagreement with the treatment adopted? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you explain why?	OP.	Non-discrimination.
Q37	In the e-commerce scenario, do you know measures that you would adopt to ensure traceability of those responsible for processing user data in relation to compliance with regulations? If so, could you describe how this would be done?	OP.	Accountability.
Q38	Do you know measures to measure the effectiveness of the treatment adopted by those responsible? If so, could you mention them?	OP.	Accountability.
Q39	Do you consider it important to maintain traceability for the duration of the data processing process?	L.	Accountability.
Q40	Have you implemented the functionality of traceability of those responsible, while the data processing process is ongoing, in any other application? If so, what were the difficulties encountered? If not, could you explain why it was not necessary?	OP.	Accountability.

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